

Climate suitability technical report of *Resseliella citrifrugis*

Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors and managers to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). An extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Resseliella citrifrugis*. The data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *R. citrifrugis* in the EU.

Note on this report

This document includes a description of the climate suitability analysis methodology applied to *R. citrifrugis*. The analysis was conducted in the context of the *EFSA Pest risk assessment of Resseliella citrifrugis for the European Union* (EFSA et al., 2023). For a complete description and discussion of the results of the present analysis, inserted in the framework of a pest risk assessment, please refer to the related PRA.

Methods

Systematic literature review

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *R. citrifrugis*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records of the EPPO Global database¹ and CABI².

Table 1: List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search

Databases	Platforms
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science
Biosis	
CAB Abstracts	
Chinese Science Citation Database	
Current Content Connect	
FSTA- the food science resource	
Korean Journal Database	
Medline	
Russian Science Citation Index	
SciELO Citation Index	
Scopus	Scopus

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

CABI², CABI Thesaurus³, and CABI Invasive Species Compendium⁴ did not contain any information on the pest by the time the bibliographic search was performed. The EPPO Global Database¹ was used as source of information (Table 2) in building the search string for the pest. The query used in the scientific databases contained only the scientific and the only international common name found for *R. citrifrugis*. No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents that could include information useful for the purposes of this search as secondary information, especially in the case of pest distribution.

Table 2: Taxonomy, EPPO Code and main hosts of *Resseliella citrifrugis*.

Scientific name	Resseliella citrifrugis (Jiang)
Other scientific names	NA
International common names	Citrus fruit midge
Taxonomy	Kingdom: Animalia Phylum: Arthropoda Subphylum: Hexapoda Class: Insecta Order: Diptera Family: Cecidomyiidae
EPPO code	RESSCI
Crop hosts	Citrus maxima, Citrus reticulata, Citrus sinensis, Citrus tangerina, Citrus trifoliata, Citrus unshiu

Table 3 shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search, and the number of documents obtained.

Table 3: Research strings used for the bibliographic databases consulted and date of launch.

Platform & Date	Set	Query	Results
Web of Science 20/12/2022	#1	TS=("Resseliella citrifrugis")	<u>9</u>
	#2	TS=("citrus fruit midge")	<u>2</u>
	#3	TS=("Resseliella citrifrugis" OR "citrus fruit midge")	<u>9</u>
Scopus 20/12/2022	#1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Resseliella citrifrugis")	<u>2</u>
	#2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("citrus fruit midge")	<u>1</u>
	#3	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Resseliella citrifrugis" OR "citrus fruit midge")	<u>2</u>

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndoNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates. The remaining references were then imported (as a compressed Endnote library) in the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2021) and screened.

Document screening

Document screening followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question “*Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?*”.

The first step was based on titles and abstracts. It was applied to identify the presence of elements indicating the potential availability of information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest in the full text. In case of positive answer, the type of information potentially available was specified (i.e., Physiology/Ecology, Distribution, or Other) (see **Error! Reference source not found.** as an example).

³ <https://www.cabi.org/cabithesaurus/mtwdk.exe?yi=home>

⁴ <https://www.cabi.org/publishing-products/invasive-species-compendium/>

Reference Details

RefID: 1, The integrated control of citrus fruit midge
L. U. ShengJin

Attachments
PDF - 1-The integrated control of citrus fruit midge South China Fruits.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotable Version)

Full Text Links
DOI.org

Reference Label(s):
Add Labels here

In recent years, in the area of Jiangyong, China, and adjacent counties the citrus fruit [gall] midge [Resseliella citrifrugis] has caused serious damage to citrus fruits. Fruits of Xiangyou pummelo suffered 10-50% damage. The midge has 3-4 generations and 4-5 population peaks per year and the most damaging period is in mid-June to early August. Application of 50% phoxim (7.5-15kg/hm² + water 3750-7500kg) to the whole area of the orchard proved an effective method of control.

Submit Form and go to Datarama order or Skip to Next

1. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
Yes No Unclear

2. Specify what type of information
Physiology/Ecology Distribution Others

Figure 1: Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR, Version 2.35, Evidence Partners; 2021, <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

Selecting the answer “yes” meant that the reference was automatically moved to the next level of screening (i.e., full text screening). When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening (**Error! Reference source not found.**) was based on the full text of the documents previously selected.

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Submit Form and go to Datarama order or Skip to Next

1. INHERITED FROM TIAB SCREENING
Selection criteria in tiab
Physiology/Ecology Distribution Others

2. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?
Yes No Unclear (to be consulted)

3. What type of information
Physiology/Ecology Distribution Other

Figure 2: Full-text Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR, Version 2.35, Evidence Partners; 2021, <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed on the documents passing the full-text screening and data were saved in two files. One Excel sheet describing all the relevant extracted information, hereafter referred to as Master file (ANNEX A), and one other .csv file was used to record data on pest distribution (ANNEX B).

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file

Field name	Description	Type
RefID	Record ID. The RefID number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated by “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated by “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
Other	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated by “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on relative humidity or moisture (indicated by “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean

Table 5: Resseliella citrifugis observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
Obs_ID	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
Continent	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
Country	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
State	State where the organism observation was reported	String
Observation	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
Admin.level	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation (‘location’ in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Admin.source	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (FAO GAUL layer)	String
Admin.code	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation (‘NA’ in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Lat	Latitude of the organism observation	Double
Long	Longitude of the organism observation	Double
Google_Earth_coord	Google Earth coordinates were used only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were already indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
RefID	The RefID number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Table 4.	Integer
Species_status1	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area of observation (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
Species_status2	Classifies the organism persistence in the area of observation (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear)	String
Notes	Flagged records (with ‘x’) include additional information saved in the support table	Boolean
Uncertain	Flagged records (with ‘x’) refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g., records from museums, interceptions, unclear information)	Boolean

Table 4 shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the Master file, while the distribution file (Table 5) contains data on the georeferenced observations of the pest. To further detail the analysis, an effort was made to categorize, when possible, the observations based on the organism status. Hence, two classifications for the pest status were created. The first one (Species_status1) based on the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear), the second (Species_status2) based on the reported persistence of the organism in the observed

location (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear). An additional table associated to the distribution table and including additional notes and information on specific records was also created as a supporting material.

Climate Classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool was used to output climate suitability maps based on the Köppen-Geiger climate classification approach (EFSA and Maiorano, 2022). The approach is based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification by Kottke et al. (2006), rescaled after Rubel et al. (2017), and based on the period 1986–2010 (<http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>).

The climate types present in the observed locations of *Resseliella citrifrugis* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment was the EU, the output maps included only climate types that are present in this area. Administrative units where the pest was observed were highlighted with black borders, while point observations were indicated with red dots.

Degree-days

Given the scarcity of information on the biology and on the ecophysiology of *R. citrifrugis*, degree-days (DD) accumulation above 0°C was calculated for Europe and China. Accumulated DD were calculated with the CLIMEX software using the climate dataset available in CLIMEX, CM30 1995H V2 WO (www.climond.org), package v4.1 (Kriticos et al., 2012). Accumulated degree-days were used to compare the thermal characteristics of the areas where the pest was observed with the ones of EU.

Results

Systematic literature review

Error! Reference source not found. summarises the results of the systematic literature search in a PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009). A total of 26 documents were retrieved both from the two scientific databases (Web of Science and Scopus) and from grey literature. Nine documents were found through Web of Science, two from Scopus, and fifteen from the grey literature. After the exclusion of duplicates, 21 documents were assessed in the first level screening (title and abstract) and of these 19 were further screened at the full text level. At the full text level, six documents were excluded from the data extraction because of i.e., the absence relevant information or the unavailability of the full text. Data were then extracted from 13 references. Out of these, ten contained information on the distribution of the pest and 5 were reporting information on its eco-physiology.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure 3: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Resseliella citrifugis*.

Observed distribution data

In total, 82 observation points were extracted from the retrieved through the literature search. More specifically, 41 administrative units were identified through their FAO Global Administrative Unit Layer code (<https://data.apps.fao.org/catalog/dataset/gaul-codes>). The remaining 41 are point observations reporting specific coordinates, or small administrative units (e.g., counties) for which coordinates from Google Earth or from the reference were used. As shown in Figure 4, *R. citrifugis* is only present in eight regions of southern China. These are Fujian Sheng, Guizhou Sheng, Sichuan Sheng, Guangdong Sheng, Guangxi Zhuangzu Zizhiqu, Zhejiang Sheng, Jiangxi Sheng, Hunan Sheng.

Figure 4: Observed distribution of *Resseliella citrifugis*. The map on the left (1) shows point observations (with coordinates) where the pest was reported. The map on the right (2) shows the distribution at the administrative unit level.

Köppen-Geiger climate types

Figure 5 shows that the humid subtropical (Cfa) climate is predominant in the area where the pest was observed. The hot semi-arid (BSh), the cold semi-arid (BSk), and the oceanic (Cfb) climates are only sparsely present in the Chinese regions where the pest is established.

Figure 5: World distribution of Köppen–Geiger climate types also present in Europe where *Resseliella citrifugis* was observed. Red dots indicate point observations of the pest (coordinates). Black borders indicate administrative units where the pest was observed. Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climate type shown in the map.

Interestingly, as *Citrus sp.* are considered to be the only hosts for *R. citrifugis*, none of the Köppen-Geiger climate types present in the areas of observations, are found in the European citrus producing areas which show Mediterranean climates (Csa, Csb, Csc), (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mediterranean climate types (Hot summer-Csa, Warm summer-Csb, and Cold summer-Csc) according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. Most of the citrus producing areas (NUTS 2 with black borders) fall under those climates. Red dots and red shapes respectively show point observations and administrative units where the pest was observed.

Degree-days

Accumulated degree-days above 0°C were used to compare the thermal conditions in Europe, and especially the citrus producing areas in the Mediterranean basin, to the areas where *R. citrifrugis* was observed in China. The choice of 0°C as base temperature was based on the host range of the pest, reported to only impact *Citrus sp.*

Figure 7: Degree-days maps for Europe (on the left) and China (on the right) with a base temperature of 0°C. Legend shows the observed distribution in China (both point locations and administrative units) and the citrus producing areas in Europe at NUTS 2 level. The Degree-days (DD) scale is based on 1000 jumps. 146 DD is the number of DD to complete one generation of *Resseliella citrifrugis*.

Figure 7 shows that the coastal areas of Europe and the Mediterranean basin have a thermal accumulation similar to the one of the areas of distribution of *R. citrifrugis*. Furthermore, these areas coincide with the ones where *Citrus sp.* are cultivated.

Content of the *Resseliella citrifrugis* Zenodo repository

[Resseliella_citrifrugis _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#)

The file contains the methodology and results of the literature search used for the Climate Suitability Analysis of *Resseliella citrifrugis*. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Four maps illustrate the results of the climate suitability analysis. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2022). For an exhaustive and more comprehensive discussion of the results of the climate suitability analysis.

[Resseliella_citrifrugis _ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx](#)

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in [Resseliella_citrifrugis _ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#).

[Resseliella_citrifrugis _ANNEX_B_Observations.csv](#)

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution at a global level. Both punctual locations and administrative units are included.

Maps in .jpeg format

- [Resseliella_citrifrugis _CLIMEX_DD_Europe_China.png](#)
- [Resseliella_citrifrugis _KG.png](#)
- [Resseliella_citrifrugis _Mediterranean_climates.png](#)
- [Resseliella_citrifrugis _Observations.png](#)

[Resseliella_citrifrugis _PRA.gpkg](#)

This is a GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

References

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